

CHEMOTHERAPY OF BACTERIAL INFECTIONS. PART II. CHEMISTRY OF SOME ORGANO-SELENIUM COMPOUNDS RELATED TO SULPHANILAMIDE.

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The chemistry of some 4:4'-substituted diphenylphenyl diselenides, selenides, 4-substituted seleninic, selenonic acids and selenophenols has been described.

Antibacterial or antiprotozoal drugs mostly conform to the structure I (X = As, Sb, Bi, Hg or S; Y = OH, NH₂):

It appears that the nature of these characteristic residues (I, X) exerts a profound influence on the capacity of a drug for causing competitive inhibition of a vital enzymic function in bacterial metabolism in which *p*-amino-benzoic acid is rendered inoperative. It was felt desirable to ascertain how the therapeutic action is augmented by the replacement of these residues (I, X) by those of other related elements *e.g.*, selenium and tellurium which possess intrinsic antibacterial action.

Despite a large volume of work on sulphanilamide compounds, very few systematic attempts appear to have been made to study selenium and tellurium analogues similar to the arsenical, antimony and bismuth drugs, and in the present communication the results of a preliminary study of the chemistry of some selenium compounds are reported.

4:4'-Diacetyldiaminodiphenyl diselenide, m.p. 204-6° (II, R =

NHAc), is easily prepared from 4-acetylamino-phenyl selenocyanate (III; R = NHAc) obtained by the interaction of 4-acetylamino-phenyldiazonium acetate and potassium selenocyanate (Challenger and Peters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1375).

The free diamine (II, R = NH₂) may be readily obtained from the diacetyl derivative by hydrolysis (*cf.* Keimatsu, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1933; 53, 203).

The diacetylaminodiphenyl diselenide as well as the selenocyanate (III, R=NHAc) readily furnish the monobromo (IV) and tribromo (V) compounds, which unlike the corresponding nitro compounds (III and II, R=NO₂), give very little of the seleninic acid (II, R=NHAc) with boiling water, but give instead, a substance (m.p. 168-70°) which is being investigated.

Among the acids of this series (*cf.* Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 116, 166; Challenger and Peters, *loc. cit.*), 4-acetylaminophenylseleninic acid (VI, R=NHAc) proved difficult to isolate in a state of purity but the corresponding benzoyl derivative (VI, R=NHPhCO) is easily isolated. The selenonic acids (VII, R=NO₂, NHAc, NPhCO) are readily obtained as their potassium salts by the oxidation of the seleninic acids with aqueous permanganate (Pyman, *loc. cit.*).

Of the selenophenols (VIII) investigated, the 4-nitroselenophenol (VIII, R = NO₂) is found to be extremely unstable being converted

immediately into the diselenide (II, R=NO₂).

However, 4:4'-dinitrodiphenyl selenide (IX, R=R'=NO₂) has been prepared *via* (VIII, R=NO₂), which is an intermediate product. This method of preparation of selenides is being extended to include mixed ones (IX). The results of these experiments will be published later. For the preparation of selenium analogues of sulpanilamide, potassium 4-nitrophenylseleninate has been reacted with phosphorus pentachloride. The product formed is (XI) instead of (X).

In presence of aqueous ammonia or ice-water (XI) gives only a mixture of 4:4'-dinitrodiphenyl diselenide (II, R=NO₂) and 4-dinitrophenylseleninic acid (VI, R=NO₂) by disproportionation (*cf.* Behaghalt and Seibert, *Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 708).

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4:4'-Dinitrodiphenyl Diselenide (II, $R = NO_2$).—A few preliminary experiments carried out to ascertain whether the substance could be obtained directly from 4-nitrophenyldiazonium acetate and sodium polyselenide by the method of Schoeller (*Ber.*, 1919, 52, 1517) were not satisfactory as yields were invariably low. It was eventually prepared from 4-nitrophenyl selenocyanate (III, $R = NO_2$). Interaction of 4-nitrochloro- or bromobenzene and sodium selenide in alcoholic solution in presence of excess of selenium appears to give (IX, $R = R' = NO_2$) mixed with a little of (II, $R = NO_2$) (*cf.* Baker and Moffit, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1930, 1726).

4-Acetylaminophenyl selenocyanate (III, $R = NHAc$), described by Challenger and Peters (*loc. cit.*), was prepared more satisfactorily as follows. The diazonium chloride solution, prepared from *p*-acetylphenylenediamine (10 g.), was rendered neutral to congo red by the addition of sodium acetate and poured in a thin stream into a warm solution of potassium selenocyanate (9.8 g. in 30 c.c. of water at 60°) with stirring. After allowing the mixture to stay for 12 hours at room temperature, the precipitated light yellow solid was collected, washed thoroughly with cold water and crystallised twice from hot spirit (*aurit*), m.p. 205.6° , yield 12.5 g.

4-Aminoselenophenol (VIII, $R = NH_2$).—A solution of the above selenocyanate (10 g.) and 2.5*N*-alcoholic sodium hydroxide (50 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 6 hours. After partial evaporation of alcohol under reduced pressure, water (50 c.c.) was added and the solution exactly neutralised with acetic acid and aqueous ammonia. The precipitated selenophenol was quickly collected and crystallised from air-free dilute alcohol. After drying in a desiccator filled with nitrogen, it had m.p. $76-78^\circ$. (Found: N, 8.0. C_6H_7NSe requires N, 8.13 per cent). The aminoselenophenol is soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid, but from concentrated solution, the hydrochloride crystallises out.

4-Acetylaminoselenophenol (VIII, $R = NHAc$).—In the above experiment if only $\frac{1}{3}$ of the quantity of alcoholic potassium hydroxide was employed and the time of boiling reduced to only $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the hydrolysis stops at the stage of 4-acetylaminoselenophenol. It crystallises from dilute alcohol (nitrogen atmosphere) in pale yellow spangles, m.p. $160-65^\circ$. (Found: N, 6.4. C_6H_8ONSe requires N, 6.55 per cent). The sample of the substance, as obtained above, dissolves almost completely in air-free sodium hydroxide solution leaving but a few specks.

The selenophenol can also be obtained by a careful reduction of the selenocyanate with ammonium sulphide. If this reduction is carried in a

more drastic manner, some 4:4'-diacetyldiaminodiphenyl selenide (IX, $R=R'=NHAc$), m.p. 219° , is obtained (*cf.* D. R. P., 633,344) (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2Se$ requires N, 8.07 per cent).

4:4'-Di-(acetylamino)phenyl Diselenide (II, $R=NHAc$).—The above selenophenol was oxidised with dilute hydrogen peroxide in a similar manner to that described by Keimatsu *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). It was crystallised first from dilute acetic acid and then from dilute alcohol (charcoal). From the latter solvent it crystallised in pale yellow spangles or long plates, m.p. $204-5^{\circ}$ with previous softening at $180-82^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 6.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2Se_2$ requires N, 6.72 per cent). It is easily soluble in most organic solvents and very sparingly in boiling water.

4:4'-Diaminodiphenyl Diselenide (II, $R=NH_2$) was obtained directly from selenocyanate (III, $R=NHAc$; *cf.* Keimatsu *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) by first following the procedure described under 4-aminoselenophenol. The product without isolation was subjected to the action of atmospheric oxygen or hydrogen peroxide as described by Keimatsu. It is freely soluble in the usual organic solvents except petrol. From benzene, it crystallised in rosettes of pale orange-yellow crystals, but from lukewarm dilute alcohol it separated in pale yellow leaflets. The acid solutions of the amine easily decomposed and selenium was deposited. The sparingly soluble sulphate of the amine had m.p. $210-15^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{12}H_{12}N_2Se_2$, H_2SO_4 requires N, 6.33 per cent). The diacetyl derivative, prepared directly from the pure diamine, m.p. 80° , and acetic anhydride in pyridine solution in the ice-cold temperature for 3 days, required many crystallisations from alcohol. The dibenzoyl derivative, prepared in a similar way, separated from pyridine (charcoal) in pale yellow amorphous powder, m.p. $265-67^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{26}H_{26}O_2N_2Se_2$ requires N, 4.81 per cent). Dicaproyl (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{24}H_{32}O_2N_2Se_2$ requires N, 5.2 per cent) and divaleeroyl derivative (Found: N, 5.3. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2Se_2$ requires N, 5.49 per cent), obtained in a like manner, crystallised in leaflets from dilute alcohol, m.p. $175-77^{\circ}$ and $172-73^{\circ}$ respectively.

Potassium 4-Nitrophenylselenonate (VII, $R=NO_2$).—4-Nitrophenylseleninic acid was prepared according to the method of Behaghalt and Siebert (*loc. cit.*). This acid (25 g.) was neutralised with ammonia and oxidised with hot aqueous solution of potassium permanganate solution (12.4 g.). After boiling for a short time, manganese dioxide was filtered and the filtrate carefully evaporated under reduced pressure till crystallisation started. The colourless prism-like crystals were collected after cooling, washed with a little ice-cold water and dried. It crystallised with water of crystallisation which was lost gradually even at the room temperature. (Found: N, 5.0. $C_6H_4O_2NKSe$ requires N, 4.86 per cent).

4-Benzoylamino phenylseleninic Acid (VI, R=NHPhCO).—Dry, powdered 4:4'-di-(benzoylamino phenyl) diselenide (II, R=NHPhCO) (10 g.) was gradually stirred into concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 40 c.c.) at -6° to -3° and the ice-cold mixture after keeping for 24 hours in an ice-chest was neutralised by dropping into ammonia maintained at 0-5°. The solution was filtered through charcoal and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated powder was washed twice with ice-cold water and crystallised from boiling water. It separated in pale hay-coloured shining plates, m.p. 186° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2NSe$ requires N, 4.54 per cent).

Potassium 4-benzoyl phenylselenonate (VII, R=NHPhCO), prepared in a similar manner to the 4-nitro analogue, separated in dirty white crystals from water. (Found after drying at 110°: N, 4.0. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4NKSe$ requires N, 3.86 per cent).

Silver 4-Acetyl amino phenylseleninate (VI, R=NHAc).—After following the same procedure described under 4-benzoyl analogue, the sparingly soluble silver salt was precipitated as a powder which decomposed on keeping. (Found: Ag, 29.9. $C_8H_8O_2NAgSe$ requires Ag, 30.27 per cent).

4-Amino phenylseleninic acid (VI, R=NH₂) was obtained as barium salt by hydrolysis of the benzoyl or acetyl derivatives with barium hydroxide. [Found after drying: Ba, 25.5. $(C_8H_8O_2NSe)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 25.25 per cent].

4:4'-Dinitrodiphenyl Selenide (IX, R=R'=NO₂).—A mixture of 4-nitrophenyl selenocyanate (2.28 g), *p*-bromonitrobenzene (2.05 g.) and potassium carbonate (1.1 g.) in aqueous alcoholic solution was refluxed for 2 days. The pale greenish yellow crystalline product was collected while still hot, washed once with a little hot alcohol and then with water, and finally crystallised twice from ethyl acetate (charcoal). The selenide separated in shining pale yellow prisms, m.p. 175° (Baker and Moffit, *loc. cit.*, recorded 170-71°). A mixture of the selenide and 4:4'-dinitrodiphenyl diselenide (II, R=NO₂) melted at 150-53° and it could not be separated into components easily by crystallisation.

4:4'-Diaminodiphenyl Selenide (IX, R=R'=NH₂).—After the hydrolysis of the diacetyl derivative by alcoholic potash. the product was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in yellowish shining plates, m.p. 115-17°. (Found: N, 10.4. $C_{12}H_{12}N_2Se$ requires N, 10.64 per cent). It was also obtained from the corresponding nitro compound by reduction. The statement of Baker and Moffit (*loc. cit.*), about the reduction of *pp'*-dinitrodiphenyl selenide would appear to be erroneous. It is likely they mean only the reduction of diselenide (II, R=NO₂) and not the monoselenide (IX, R=R'=NO₂).

4-Acetylaminophenyl Selenotribromide (V).—To a well-cooled mixture of 4-acetylaminophenyl selenocyanate (III, R=NHAc, 7.8 g.) and chloroform (25 c.c.), bromine (3.3 c.c.) was added and after 24 hours, the separated orange-red rosettes of crystals (m.p. 130-32°, decomp. with previous softening at 100°) were collected and washed with chloroform-benzene mixture. (Found: Br, 54.2. $C_7H_4ONBr_3Se$ requires Br, 54.89 per cent).

4-Acetylaminophenyl Selenobromide (IV).—Finely powdered tribromide (V) lost two atoms of bromine when kept for a week in an evacuated desiccator over potassium hydroxide. The orange-red colour of the product turned to light yellow. (Found: Br, 29.1. $C_7H_4ONBrSe$ requires Br, 28.86 per cent). With boiling water, the bromide hydrolysed to a neutral substance, which separated in thick orange-red prisms from hot benzene or in pale yellow long plates from hot water, m.p. 168-69°. The nature of the product is under investigation.

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